

Levelling Up Health: A Review of UK Datasets on Place-based Measures of Health Inequality

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Summary

The UK government has committed to reducing health disparities between places in the UK by 2030 as part of its Levelling Up agenda. Spatial data can be used to better understand a place's health, social-economic outcomes, and the relationship between them. Knowledge of what data is out there is key to track the government's progress, as well as to inform the policy decisions that will enable that progress to happen. This paper forms the beginnings of a comprehensive resource of UK spatial datasets that can be combined, classified, and analysed in the effort to reduce geographic health inequalities.

KEYWORDS: health inequalities, spatial datasets

1. Introduction

The UK government has committed to reducing place-based health inequalities in their Levelling Up white paper (DLUHC, 2022). It targets health directly, with a commitment to narrowing the gap in healthy life expectancy between areas by 2030, but it also targets the wider determinants of health by committing to narrowing the gaps in pay, employment, housing, and wellbeing (Ralston et al., 2022). Understanding the ways in which we can measure these spatial variations is necessary to track any progress towards the goals, as well as to design the policy decisions that will enable them to be achieved. This review forms the beginnings of a comprehensive resource of UK spatial datasets that can be used to understand the multi-directional relationships between a place's health and its social-economic outcomes. Variation in health in places is attributable to more than deprivation (e.g., Bamba et al., 2023) and we must look to a range of indicators to assess these differences most thoroughly.

The 2021 Census data is the most granular and representative data on this issue that we have, but it will become less useful over time. Therefore, we should aim to have a good understanding of which datasets to combine with the census by the time the ONS releases it all, if we are to produce timely findings. We should also have a thorough understanding of which up-to-date datasets to look to by the time that combining new data with census data becomes redundant. Reducing health inequalities is not a fast process, but up-to-date data will still be necessary if the government wishes to track any progress towards reducing health inequalities. To that end, wider knowledge of the strengths and weaknesses of relevant datasets is key.

2. Methodology

The datasets were selected while creating a literature review about the ways in which we can apply data visualisation to place-based health inequalities in the UK, as well as through conversations with experts in the field. This section outlines the criteria used when selecting datasets for inclusion in the review, and then the criteria upon which they were evaluated.

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2.1 Criteria for selection

Datasets were selected for inclusion if they were available at local authority level, were updated at least every 10 years, and could potentially inform research on health inequalities. NHS England publish a range of data, such as ambulance handover delays, waiting times for consultant-led referral, and waiting times in Accident & Emergency at the NHS Trust-level. While these do have a spatial component (as demonstrated in a BBC News (2022) tracker in which users enter their postcode and see the performance of local services), any one location can be served by multiple Trusts, resulting in an unclear geography. A researcher at the House of Commons Library attempted to map ambulance waiting times with point data at each NHS Trust’s “main location” (Baker, 2021), but this is a major simplification. Selecting datasets that are available at least at the local authority level is useful since this is the scale at which many policy decisions are taken.

The Small Area Health Statistics Unit at Imperial College London published the *Environment and Health Atlas for England and Wales* in 2014, which maps long-term risks for 14 health conditions and 5 environmental agents at census-ward level. While this is in a very useful geography with reliable data, its sources are based on records from 1985-2009, and so does not update sufficiently regularly to track medium-term trends.

The selected datasets are all free to access in financial terms, but a minority require successful application to the data provider.

2.2 Criteria for dataset evaluation

Once selected for inclusion, datasets were assessed on their granularity and their velocity (how often they update). We do not attempt to assess their “importance” to the measurement of health inequalities, since innovative analysis should consider all datasets that may be of some relevance.

3. An assessment of key datasets

Table 1 shows a selection of datasets from the review.

Table 1 UK datasets on place-based measures of health inequality

Dataset	Indicators	Granularity	Velocity
2021 Census	Housing, education, demography, employment, travel to work, disability, and self-reported health	● LSOA	○ Decennially
<i>Population health</i>			
ONS Longitudinal Study	Same as census, plus birth and mortality data	● LSOA	○ Decennially, with life events data linked annually
Hospital Episode Statistics	Records of patients attending A&E or admitted for treatment at NHS hospitals	● LSOA	● Monthly
Quality and Outcomes	Range of indicators, including clinical (e.g. heart failure,	● GP practice (some missing)	● Annually

Framework (QOF)	hypertension), public health (e.g. smoking, obesity), and others domains		
Fingertips indicators (Public Health Outcomes Frameworks)	Includes frailty, healthy eating, STIs (diagnoses and testing rate)	☐ Upper tier local authority (lower tier where possible)	● Quarterly
Fingertips indicators (Local Health)	Includes life expectancy, fertility rate, self harm, overcrowding	● MSOA	● Quarterly
ONS drug poisoning deaths	Deaths related to drug poisoning in England and Wales	☐ Local authority	☐ Annually

Social determinants

Understanding Society	Extensive list including community cohesion, neighbourhood trust, nutrition, health behaviours, and wellbeing	● LSOA (but small sample size)	☐ Annually
Community Life Survey	Includes community cohesion, volunteering, and trust in institutions	● LSOA (but small sample size)	☐ Annually
ONS Subnational Indicators	Includes obesity, school absences, life satisfaction, travel to work	☐ Local authority	Varies. As of January 2023, all indicators cover some period within 2018 and 2022.
Statutory homelessness statistics	Homelessness and rough sleeping	☐ Local authority	● Quarterly
OpenStreetMap	Includes green space categorised into many types	● Precise location	● Real-time (volunteered geographic information)
Police UK data	Includes public order offences, drug crime, and total offences	● LSOA	● Quarterly
Food hygiene rating	Rating for all businesses that sell food	● Precise location	● Daily

Energy Performance Certificates (EPC)	Includes energy efficiency ratings, average floor area sizes, and fuel costs. Represents about 60% of all homes in England and Wales	● LSOA	● Quarterly
Small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) lending by banks	Lending by banks	● Postcode sector	● Biannually
Environment Agency LiDAR imagery	Includes the Vegetation Object Model, which identifies tree canopy cover	● 1m raster in GB (>95% coverage in England)	● Quarterly
UKCEH Land Cover Map	Land cover classes	● 10m raster	● Annually
Bus Open Data	Timetables, live locations, and fares for routes	● Precise location	● Real-time
Access to Health Assets and Hazards (AHAH)	Accessibility to features including gambling outlets, bars, health services, and green space	● LSOA	● Annually

4. Discussion

In general, there is a lack of quality, granular, spatial datasets concerning health and social-economic factors. For example, there is limited data relating to mental health and well-being at the local authority level (Murray et al., 2022). Furthermore, while there is a good amount of available spatial data about mortality, there is not enough on morbidity (ibid.). Air pollution data is available at high granularity in many UK cities but, to our knowledge, users must download this data from multiple different providers if they wish to compare them. The Levelling Up white paper calls for an increase in the quantity of granular data available.

Nonetheless, when exploring the relationships between the health of a place and its social and economic outcomes, meaningful insights will arise through the innovative combination and classification of the datasets we do have. Five examples of combining spatial health datasets are listed in the appendix. Impact on Urban Health created their *Urban Health Index* for Lambeth and Southwark, which has been used to identify and inspect health differences in neighbourhoods with similar levels of deprivation (Tarkington, 2021). The ONS' Health Index for England uses factor analysis to weight indicators and place them in useful categories of 'healthy lives', 'healthy people' and 'healthy places', but it is only available at the local authority level. Such indices can have drawbacks, such as masked variation among indicators as well as limited granularity and timeliness. However, they also have the power to further the conversation on improving health (Nightingale & Merrifield, 2022) and be used as a measure to assess the success of a policy.

The next steps of this research are to better understand how researchers, funders, and policymakers can make better use of the available data. A small part of that lies in how these measures of health – and any associated experimental results – are presented through data visualisation. We are undertaking a series of interviews with these stakeholders to understand how they produce and consume visualisations of population health data, and what challenges and opportunities may shape how health inequalities

research is translated into policy. The data presented in this paper will be useful case studies for experimenting with visualisation.

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Biographies

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Appendix

Table 2 Place-based indices of health in the UK

Index (provider)	Domain	Region	Granularity	Velocity	Weighting
Health Index for England (ONS)	Broad definition of health including outcomes, behaviours, and wider determinants. Key dimensions are ‘healthy people’, ‘healthy lives’, and ‘healthy places’	England	Lower-tier Local Authority	Annually	Yes (factor analysis)
Urban Health Index (Impact on Urban Health)	Based on the Social Progress Index, which is notably independent of economic indicators. Key dimensions are ‘basic human needs’, ‘foundations of wellbeing’, and ‘opportunity’	Lambeth and Southwark	MSOA	Unclear (published 2021)	Yes (principal component analysis)
Small Area Mental Health Index (Place-Based Longitudinal Data Resource)	Mental health	England	LSOA	Annually	Yes (factor analysis)
English Indices of Deprivation (DLUHC)	Clinical health outcomes (morbidity, disability, premature mortality)	England	LSOA	Every 3-5 years	Yes (factor analysis)
Environmental Justice Score (Birmingham City Council Geospatial Team)	Birmingham CC’s conceptualisation of environmental justice (green space, flood risk, urban heat island effect, excess years of life lost, index of multiple deprivation)	Birmingham	Ward	Unclear (published 2022)	None